

Reaction of rice cultures to major pests. Coimbatore, India, 1987.

Variety	Damage rating ^a		
	BPH	WBPH	LF
PM5845	3	1	5
PM1409	3	3	5
PM1004	5	1	7
PM1123	7	1	9
PM1381	9	7	7
Nootripathu	7	3	7
PMK1 (PM1023)	9	1	9
TKM9 (local check)	9	9	7
PTB33 (resistant check)	3	3	3
ASD11 (resistant check)	3	3	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	9	9

^a Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.*

at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU. One row of susceptible check TN1, two rows of resistant checks ASD11 and PTB33, and one row of local check TKM9 were included. The experiments were replicated twice. Damage was scored on the 0-9 scale of *Standard evaluation system for rice.*

PM5845 and PM1409 showed good

levels of BPH and WBPH resistance (score: 1-3) and moderate levels of LF resistance (score: 5). PM1004 was resistant to WBPH and moderately susceptible to BPH (see table). These cultures are being evaluated under multilocation trials for their yield potential at various locations in Tamil Nadu. □

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High resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in Indonesia

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Since 1979-83 we have screened 3,872 lines and varieties originating from MORIF, Bogor Research Institute for Food Crops (BORIF), and other countries for WBPH resistance.

Seeds were sown in 15-cm rows in 40 × 30 × 7-cm plastic trays at 25 seeds/row, with 4 replications. TN1 was the susceptible check, Rexoro was the resistant check. Seven days after sowing, seedlings were infested with 5th-instar nymphs at 15-25 nymphs/seedling. Damage was scored when TN1 had 95-100% hopperburn.

Ninety-one varieties and lines were highly resistant (score = 0). Of these, 34 were from MORIF, 23 from BORIF, 27 from IRRI, and the rest from other countries (see table). □

Lines and varieties ^a highly resistant to WBPH in Maros, Indonesia.

Lines and varieties			
MORIF	BORIF	IRRI	Other countries
M57b-7-2	B40580-Kp23-1	IR93240-6-3	
M57b-38-2	B3894d-17c-Sm-37-3	IR9224-117-2-3-3-2	
M57b-39-1	B3894d-17c-Sm-48-3	IR8608-79-3-2	Utri Rajapan
M67b-2-2	B3894d-17c-Sm-54-2	IR9782-111-2-1-2	Abu tmuau
M170-181	B3894d-17c-Sm-63-2	IR9814-11-3	BKNBR1008-21
M170-191	B3894d-17c-Sm-64-2	IR13146-29-3	BKNBR1031-75-4
M170-192	B4104c-Sm-40-3	IR13537-44-2	Acc. 15286
M43c-26-2	B4111c-Sm-6-2	IR14632-22-3	MRC603-303
M7d-35-8	B4111c-Sm-8-1	IR1475349-2	IET4086 (CR14062)
M7d-35-9	B4111c-Sm-22-1	IR15313-14-2	
M7d-44-1	B4111c-Sm-26-1	IR15795-151-2-3	
M7d-44-2	B4111c-Sm-66-1	IR15795-199-3-3	
M7d-76-1	B4126c-Sm-33-2	IR13240-10-1	
M7d-76-2	B3102d-2-1-Blk	IR13429-47-3	
M7d-76-3	B3616f-Kp-148-2	IR2307-72-2-2-1	
M164-68	B3727d-Pn-19-4-2	IR5853-162-2-3	
M164-76	B3909b-Mr-269-2-1	IR13641-17	
M164-115	B3909b-Mr-269-2-2	IR4432-28-5	
M164-116	B3909b-Mr-269-2-3	IR5853-59-2-2	
M7d-78-1	B3115e-Kp-44-2	IR5853-33-2-2	
M7d-78-2	B3667d-Kp-131-1-1	IR4744-179-1-5-2	
M7d-78-3	B3328e-Sm-11-3	IR2793-18-3	
M7d-83-1	B3065b-Ck-1-K-5-2	IR9093-3-2-2	
M7d-83-3		IR9093-211-6	
M7d-83-4		IR8608-75-3-1	
M7d-83-5		IR13427-60-1	
M175d-1138		IR36	
M175d-1139			
M175d-1140			
M175d-1144			
M175d-1145			
M175d-1073			
M175d-1076			

^a Scored zero by the *Standard evaluation system for rice.*

Reaction of selected rices to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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We evaluated 31 rice accessions for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* in the screenhouse, using the modified seedbox technique. Pregerminated seeds were sown in seedboxes. More than 20 plants of each accession were tested in 2 replications.

Seedlings were infested 7 d after sowing with 2d- to 3d-instar nymphs by evenly distributing insects through the seedbox at 6-8/seedling.

Reaction was measured when the susceptible check died, usually 8-9 d